

Optimising Fire Station Layouts to Improve Fire Service Efficiency: A Spatial Machine Learning and Genetic Algorithm Approach

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GISRUK 2026

Summary

Efficient fire services are crucial for safeguarding public safety and reducing economic losses. Fire service efficiency, commonly measured using response time and its derivatives, varies spatially across service areas due to multiple factors, including fire station locations. This non-linear relationship between fire service efficiency and fire station locations can be modelled by geo-spatial machine learning. Building on this, this study integrates a data-driven efficiency model with a genetic algorithm to optimise fire station layouts. Using the West Midlands as a case study, the proposed approach improves global fire service efficiency from 38.19% to 44.90%, demonstrating its potential to support more effective and equitable fire service planning.

KEYWORDS: Spatial Optimisation, Genetic Algorithm, Machine Learning

1 Introduction

Fire incidents represent a significant global hazard, accounting for tens of thousands of deaths and injuries each year (Shi et al., 2025). Most existing research on fire service performance focuses on response time of individual incidents and does not account for the spatial pattern of service efficiency. In our previous work (Zhao et al., 2025), we proposed a fire service efficiency metric that quantifies the proportion of historical incidents responded within the time threshold in 500-m cells. Moreover, we developed geospatial machine learning to model this efficiency based on selected spatial and social factors, achieving strong predictive performance, with cross-validated R^2 values of approximately 0.73.

Despite the revealed impact of station location on fire service efficacy, research has yet to optimise station distribution in order to enhance fire service performance. A key challenge is that most spatial optimisation frameworks (such as Maximal Cover Location Model or p-median) are based on mixed integer programming and a linear relationship between variables (Yao et al., 2019; Murray, 2013); therefore, they are not applicable for this task, as the relationship between fire service efficiency

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and fire station layout is non-linear. To address this issue, we propose a genetic algorithm that iteratively improves fire station layout and ultimately optimises the fire service efficiency. We demonstrate the efficiency of this algorithm in a case study of West Midlands. The results show that global fire service efficiency increased from 38.19% to 44.90%, with a total computation time of 4687.39 seconds.

2 Methodology

2.1 Modelling fire service efficiency

In previous work, fire incident data were aggregated into 500-metre grid cells. A fire service efficiency metric was introduced to quantify fire response performance at the local level, defined as the proportion of incidents within each grid cell that were responded to within a predefined response-time target. Fire service efficiency was then calculated for each grid cell and used as the target variable.

A random forest model was trained to model localised fire service efficiency using five selected spatial and socio-economic features. Based on prior analysis and domain knowledge, five features were adopted, including distance to the nearest fire station, nearby fire incident frequency, fire station density, and two local land use characteristics, which are the agricultural and deciduous woodland. This model was used to estimate localised fire service efficiency across grid cells and served as the surrogate model within the spatial optimisation framework.

2.2 Optimising the fire station layouts

Building on the modelled fire service efficiency, this study develops a spatial optimisation framework to improve global fire service efficiency. Each fire station is assumed to be located at the centre of a grid cell. Global fire service efficiency is defined as a demand-weighted average of localised fire service efficiency across all grid cells, and is expressed as:

$$F(S) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N w_i E_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N w_i}, \quad (1)$$

where $F(S)$ denotes the global fire service efficiency for a given fire station layout S , E_i represents the localised fire service efficiency of grid cell i , estimated using the pre-trained machine learning model, w_i denotes the demand weight associated with grid cell i , and N is the total number of grid cells considered. A genetic algorithm is employed to search for improved fire station layouts. This algorithm uses global fire service efficiency as the fitness function and iteratively improves fire station layouts using selection, crossover, and mutation operators. This process stops when no further improvement in fitness is observed over a predefined number of generations or when the maximum number of generations is reached.

3 Case study: West Midlands Fire Service

3.1 Study area and data

This case study focuses on West Midlands Combined Authority in the United Kingdom (UK). Located in the heart of England, West Midlands is a metropolitan and ceremonial county covering an area of approximately 902 square kilometres (Ordnance Survey, 2024). The historical fire incident data used in this study comprise 292,697 recorded fire-related events, including fire incidents and false alarms, occurring between 2009 and 2023. These data were obtained from the West Midlands Fire Service (WMFS).

3.2 Results

We developed a genetic algorithm to optimise the layout of 40 fire stations in the West Midlands. Changes in global fire service efficiency across generations are illustrated in Figure 1, and the optimisation process terminated after reaching 500 generations. The optimised fire station layout achieved a global fire service efficiency of 44.90%, representing a considerable improvement over the current layout (38.19%). In addition, the algorithm is computationally efficient, with a total runtime of 4687.39 seconds on a desktop computer.

Figure 2 compares the spatial distribution of fire service efficiency under the existing and optimised fire station layouts.

Figure 2(a) shows the efficiency pattern under the current station layout, characterised by a more uneven service coverage. In the current layout, two fire stations are located in close proximity near the boundary of Sandwell, resulting in overlapping service areas. In addition, a fire station in the southern part of Dudley is associated with low surrounding efficiency, indicating a spatial mismatch between station location and service demand. These spatial inefficiencies are highlighted by the red rectangular box in Figure 2(a). Figure 2(b) presents the optimised layout after optimisation, in which fire stations are more evenly distributed across the study area. This redistribution leads to an expansion of high-efficiency zones and a reduction in low-efficiency areas, particularly in previously underserved locations.

4 Conclusions and future work

This study developed a data-driven framework that integrates geospatial machine learning with genetic algorithm optimisation to improve fire service efficiency through fire station layout planning. Using the West Midlands as a case study, the proposed approach improves global fire service efficiency from 38.19% to 44.90%.

Future work will focus on extending the optimisation model by incorporating additional real-world constraints, such as budget limits and operational costs, as well as multi-objective formulations to balance efficiency and equity. Further validation will be conducted using other study areas and emergency service datasets to assess the robustness and transferability of the proposed framework.

Figure 1: Fitness over generations

5 Biography

Yuxin Zhao is a PhD candidate at Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis, University College London. Her research interests include spatial optimisation, spatial-temporal data mining, and human mobility.

Huanfa Chen is an Associate Professor in Spatial Data Science, at the Bartlett Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis (CASA), University College London. His research draws on GIScience, machine learning, and spatial optimisation to address contemporary challenges in the planning and operations of urban services, incl. policing, fire services, public health, and transport.

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(a) The fire service efficiency under the current layout

(b) The fire service efficiency under the optimal layout

Figure 2: Heatmap of fire service efficiency under different layouts